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THEORETICAL AND ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS OF IMPROVING THE FINANCIAL PROSPERITY OF THE POPULATION THROUGH POVERTY REDUCTION PROJECTS

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the theoretical and economic foundations of improving the financial prosperity of the population through projects aimed at reducing poverty. The study scientifically substantiates the level of poverty, its impact on economic growth, and its relationship with the social protection system. Mechanisms for increasing the population's income through microfinancing, subsidies, preferential loans, and social programs will also be considered. The article proposes modern approaches to combating poverty, international experience, and ways to adapt them to the conditions of Uzbekistan. As a result, the role of state policy in ensuring financial inclusion and social stability is analyzed from an economic point of view.*

Keywords: *poverty, poverty reduction projects, financial well-being, microfinancing, subsidies, loans, social policy, income.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada kambag'allikni qisqartirishga qaratilgan loyihalar orqali aholining moliyaviy farovonligini oshirishning nazariy-iqtisodiy asoslari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda kambag'allik darajasi, uning iqtisodiy o'sishga ta'siri hamda ijtimoiy himoya tizimi bilan o'zaro bog'liqligi ilmiy jihatdan asoslab berilgan. Shuningdek, mikromoliyalashtirish, subsidiyalar, imtiyozli kreditlar va ijtimoiy dasturlar orqali aholining daromadlarini oshirish mexanizmlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Maqolada kambag'allikka qarshi kurashishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari, xalqaro tajribalar hamda ularni O'zbekiston sharoitiga moslashtirish yo'llari taklif etiladi. Natijada, moliyaviy inklyuziya va ijtimoiy barqarorlikni ta'minlashda davlat siyosatining roli iqtisodiy nuqtayi nazardan tahlil qilinadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *kambag'allik, kambag'allikni qisqartirish loyihalari, moliyaviy farovonlik, mikromoliyalashtirish, subsidiyalar, kreditlar, ijtimoiy siyosat, daromadlar.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье анализируются теоретико-экономические основы повышения финансового благосостояния населения посредством проектов, направленных на сокращение бедности. В исследовании научно обоснованы уровень бедности, его влияние на экономический рост и взаимосвязь с системой социальной защиты. Также будут рассмотрены механизмы повышения доходов населения за счет микрофинансирования, субсидий, льготных кредитов и социальных программ. В статье предлагаются современные подходы к борьбе с бедностью, международный опыт и пути их адаптации к условиям Узбекистана. В результате роль государственной политики в обеспечении финансовой инклюзии и социальной стабильности анализируется с экономической точки зрения.*

Ключевые слова: бедность, проекты по сокращению бедности, финансовое благополучие, микрофинансирование, субсидии, кредиты, социальная политика, доходы.

INTRODUCTION

Poverty reduction means instilling an entrepreneurial spirit in the population, fully realizing the inner strength and potential of a person, and implementing a comprehensive economic and social policy to create new jobs'. According to the laws of economics, 'poverty breeds poverty'. This process occurs for several reasons.

First, low-income countries cannot afford to spend enough money on quality education and health care, and poor people cannot afford quality paid education and medical services, which reduces their human potential and prevents them from escaping poverty.

Secondly, as the incomes of the poor decrease, the capacity of the consumer market decreases proportionally, and as a result, the demand for industrial goods, agricultural products, and especially services decreases. This, in turn, hinders economic development, reduces budget revenues, and reduces the possibility of providing social support to the poor, creating a vicious circle.

Third, in most cases, the poor have a different outlook than their higher-income peers. For the reasons mentioned above, they are less likely to produce creative and entrepreneurial individuals. They also tend to have higher crime rates among poor families.

In other words, the factors that cause poverty hinder the development of human potential in a country, the development of productive forces, and the economic activity of the population.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Poverty is a global challenge to human development, and the eradication of poverty in all its forms worldwide has become a key goal of the United Nations' 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. There is no single definition of poverty. Some define poverty as the inability to meet basic human needs (food, clothing, housing, education, and health), while others define poverty as the lack of freedom of choice or living on less than \$1.90 a day (Deng et al., 2015).

Poverty is the inability of individuals, households, or entire communities to manage sufficient resources to meet a socially acceptable minimum standard of living. In recent years, technological developments, especially digital technologies, have facilitated social and economic development that directly generate new approaches and solutions to poverty reduction and challenge existing poverty research theories (Lopatnikov, 2003).

Technological developments, especially digital technologies, have created new approaches (and ways of looking at) poverty reduction, which challenge the existing poverty research theory, which traditionally focuses on financial assistance and relief.

Economists Sofield, T., Bauer, J., Delacy, T. (2004) have proposed a structural analysis of the labor market, the employed and unemployed population, targeted identification and accounting of the unemployed - analysis of the labor market and targeted accounting of the unemployed, forecasting the demand for labor resources

in developing sectors and industries of the economy, identifying structural problems in the labor market and preventing imbalances. British economist May J. (1999).

METHODOLOGY

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-143 dated September 23, 2024 'On bringing measures to reduce poverty and improve the prosperity of the population to a new stage', the 'From Poverty to Prosperity' program (2024) was adopted.

Actively cooperates with the International Labor Organization, forms employment programs, keeps records of vacancies, and places the unemployed in work - develops an employment program for each year by region, sector, and industry and coordinates its implementation, keeps records of and monitors available vacancies, organizes employment of unemployed citizens, and connects them with employers. Analyze the dynamics and composition of poverty, organize the development and coordination of individual plans for families to lift themselves out of poverty, conduct on-site studies of the work carried out to lift the population out of poverty, and reflect on the results. In our country, monthly information is provided to the Republican Commission

- for the implementation of the program 'From Poverty to Prosperity' (2024), methodological support for the district's activities on issues of developing entrepreneurship in the mahalla,
- ensuring employment and reducing poverty,
 - continuous analysis of improving skills and qualifications for working with promising projects,
 - development and assessment of the most important performance indicators, proposals for eliminating systemic problems identified in its activities,
 - development of professional standards,
 - training in professions and foreign languages,
 - qualification assessment,
 - development of professional standards recognized abroad with the involvement of international experts,
 - formation of a state order for training in professions and foreign languages in high demand,
 - regulation of the market for qualification assessment services based on standards, wide involvement of the private sector in the sector,
 - creation of decent working conditions,
 - study of compliance with labor standards,
 - ensuring labor rights and labor protection, introduction of decent labor principles and international standards,
 - labor development of effective mechanisms for regulating labor relations,
 - protection of labor rights,
 - as well as ensuring occupational safety and hygiene and decent working conditions.

The following analyses were carried out on the issues of ensuring employment and reducing poverty in Uzbekistan:

- Analysis of the correct, targeted, targeted structure and effectiveness of individual plans for lifting families out of poverty, as well as the timely and high-quality

implementation of work to improve the infrastructure of the most disadvantaged neighborhoods;

- Coordination of the implementation of individual plans, if necessary, ensuring effective results by making appropriate changes to them;

- Solving problems identified in the implementation of individual plans together with competent organizations and submitting proposals to the Republican Commission on solving systemic problems;

- Monitoring the effectiveness of the activities of the leadership of organizations assigned to poor families and the most disadvantaged neighborhoods;

- The Ministry created a catalog of "100 most effective microprojects" that have yielded positive results in three months by providing employment and increasing incomes of the population and taking measures to popularize them in all regions of the republic through assistant khokims.

- By 1st December, 2025, industrialized plantations, orchards and vineyards will be established on 50-100 hectares of leased agricultural land in 50 districts, and in the remaining districts in 2026;

- By 1st December, 2025, model projects will be implemented on the cultivation of highly profitable and export-oriented agricultural products on an area of at least 40 hectares in districts where land is leased on a lease basis, based on the principle of "one contour - one product";

- By 1st August, 2026, projects for the construction of at least two multi-storey complex industrial centers and the placement of entrepreneurs will be implemented in the Republic of Karakalpakstan and regions;

- in makhallas where industry has not penetrated, 1,000 agricultural product processing and small-scale production projects will be launched by 1st December, 2025, and 2,000 by 2026;

- measures will be taken to introduce and expand at least 500 handicraft and home-based projects in the makhalla itself each year;

- in 2,000 makhallas by 1st December, 2025, and in the remaining makhallas by the end of 2026, leading entrepreneurs will establish their activities in cooperation with potential entrepreneurs, exporters and brokers;

- starting from 2026, the number of makhallas specializing in relevant sectors and areas of the economy will be increased by 10% annually, attracting leading entrepreneurs;

- measures will be taken to gradually transform 50,000 self-employed citizens into small business entities each year.

In order to organize a system for training the unemployed and poor population in working professions that meet the requirements of the domestic and foreign labor market:

- a) Vocational skills centers are being established on the basis of the "Ishga Marhamat" monocenters and vocational training centers under the Ministry;

- b) In the vocational skills centers of the Ministry:

From 1st January, 2025, fast-track courses will be launched, providing for flexible training terms and times to meet the needs of employers;

From 1st March, 2025, the introduction of new practices that allow the formation of practical vocational skills directly in the workplace;

From 1st May, 2025, the introduction of internationally recognized educational programs; By January 1, 2026, through accreditation of vocational skills centers by international assessment organizations, their graduates will be issued certificates (qualification passports) recognized abroad; By 1st July, 2026, a center for assessing professional qualifications according to international standards will be established with the involvement of a qualified foreign organization, and this center will issue qualification certificates recognized in foreign countries.

On behalf of the President

a) from November 1, 2024, inspections of compliance with the legislation on labor rights and labor protection by the State Labor Inspectorate and its territorial divisions were carried out from the moment of the start of the inspection, with the notification of the Representative for the Protection of the Rights and Legal Interests of Business Entities;

b) from March 1, 2025:

Officials of the State Labor Inspectorate and its territorial divisions were authorized to conduct in-camera inspections for non-compliance with the requirements of the legislation on labor rights and labor protection, compulsory insurance of the employer's civil liability, and employment of the population;

a procedure for imposing fines on persons who violated the legislation on labor rights and labor protection, interfered with, obstructed or influenced the lawful activities of officials of the State Labor Inspectorate and its territorial divisions;

The State Labor Inspectorate and its territorial divisions were allowed to conduct control measures over the compliance of the number of workers at facilities being built, repaired or reconstructed at the expense of the State budget with the design and estimate documents and the volume of contract work, using data from the 'Shaffof Qurilish' national information system

In order to protect the domestic labor market, as well as to maintain records of foreign citizens working in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry issued certificates to legal entities and foreign citizens granting them the right to carry out labor activities in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Poverty is a burden on the social system, leading to a number of consequences, such as social injustice, limited access to education and health services, and a poor quality of life. To this end, production programs and programs to improve poverty alleviation benefit the economy and improve the livelihoods of the population.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) set by the UN set the first goal of eradicating poverty. To achieve this goal, developing countries, in particular the countries of Central Asia, are actively implementing their socio-economic programs. For Uzbekistan, poverty reduction is also an important task in ensuring the well-being of the population. Today, the country is implementing many projects in various areas, such as social protection, employment, education and healthcare. These initiatives are mainly aimed at meeting the needs of the population and are aimed at achieving significant positive results in reducing poverty.

Poverty reduction projects are important in improving the living standards of the population, as they contribute to the creation of new jobs, increasing incomes and strengthening social protection. Also, by expanding access to education and health

services, long-term economic stability can be achieved. As a result, a fair distribution of national income is ensured and important steps are taken to eliminate economic inequality. These issues are an important basis for the development and implementation of poverty reduction strategies.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The issue of ensuring the well-being of the population by reducing poverty is currently an urgent issue for developing countries such as Uzbekistan and is recognized as one of the main tasks on the way to achieving socio-economic stability in the country. Therefore, research and programs conducted on this topic can lead to new stages of economic and social development. The 'Uzbekistan – 2030' strategy sets out a wide range of measures and goals for poverty reduction. This strategy identifies a sharp reduction in poverty in the country as one of its main goals, and also sets the task of halving the poverty level by 2026 compared to 2022 and further reducing it by 2030. In this regard, special attention is paid to increasing the incomes of the needy population, supporting entrepreneurial initiatives, and ensuring employment.

In 2025, in order to develop human capital in Uzbekistan, 59.5 trillion soums will be allocated to the Ministry of Preschool and School Education, and 6.6 trillion soums to the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovations. These funds will be used to build and reconstruct 375 schools and 97 kindergartens, update textbooks, equip computer classes, attract foreign teachers, provide sports and music equipment, as well as organize clubs for students in need of social protection and support entrepreneurs opening private schools through loans and subsidies'.

In addition, the 'Neighborhood Budget' system is being implemented by the Ministry of Support of Neighborhoods and Enlightenment, together with the Ministry of Finance, the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction, and the State Tax Committee, by searching for additional sources based on the specific characteristics and potential of each neighborhood and expanding their income base on this basis Coordinated activities will be launched to ensure that the revenue parameters of the funds for solving the socio-economic problems of the mahalla are met'.

CONCLUSION

The need to amend the legislation to strengthen budget discipline was also emphasized. In particular, it was firmly established that it is necessary to put an end to the practice of directly concluding contracts at the expense of state funds and to conduct tenders openly and transparently. The main part of state expenditures - about 48.2 percent - was allocated to the social sphere and social protection of the population. More than 46 percent of these funds were directed to financing education, and more than 22 percent to financing healthcare.

One of the main means of achieving prosperity through poverty reduction is the expansion of economic opportunities. Projects aimed at education and vocational training are one of the main factors in attracting the poor population to economic activity. In particular, programs aimed at teaching women and youth entrepreneurial skills create opportunities for them to master new professions and help provide them with employment. Such projects help to shape the population as active participants in various sectors of the economy. This process, in turn, contributes to economic growth

and reduces social inequality. Also, by expanding access to and improving the quality of health services, the health of the population improves, increasing their production and income-generating opportunities.

At the same time, poverty reduction projects require the use of methods adapted to local conditions, based on successful programs implemented in international experience. In particular, in the experience of Uzbekistan, projects implemented in cooperation with international organizations, including major international financial institutions such as the World Bank and the Asian Development Bank, are of particular importance. This cooperation plays an important role in the socio-economic development of the country, increasing the effectiveness of the initiatives being implemented by attracting international resources and experience. These projects bring international resources and experience to the country and help strengthen the national development strategy.

REFERENCES:

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 2023. National database of legislative information, 01.05.2023, No. 03/23/837/0241
2. Budget Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan. No. OPX-360. 26.12.2013. Collection of Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2013. No. 52-I.
3. Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan // National database of legislative documents, 04/29/2021, No. 03/21/689/0395.
4. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-5034 dated March 15, 2021 "On the State Program for Reducing Poverty and Increasing Employment in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2021-2023".
5. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 404 dated July 1, 2022 'On additional measures to support vulnerable segments of the population'.
6. World Bank. (2020). World development report: Data for better lives. World Bank.
7. <http://www.lex.uz> - National Database of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
8. <http://www.mf.uz> - Official site of the Ministry of Economics and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
9. <http://http://www.soliq.uz> - Official site of the State Tax Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
10. <http://www.norma.uz> - Norma information and legal portal.